

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
6

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles
PUBLISHED MONTHLY

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ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

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Electronic publication, Issue 6. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on Iyun, 2026.

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ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)

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Abstract. This article examines the evolving role of public-private partnerships (PPPs) in financing and implementing infrastructure development projects across different global regions, with particular emphasis on investment trends in 2025. The study analyzes PPP investment dynamics, sectoral distribution, and regional disparities, highlighting the recovery of global PPP investments after a period of decline and the continued concentration of capital in a limited number of countries and sectors. Special attention is given to the role of development finance institutions (DFIs) and export credit agencies in supporting infrastructure financing in high-risk and capital-constrained environments, particularly in International Development Association (IDA) countries.

The findings indicate that total PPP investment volumes exceeded USD 100 billion in 2025, reflecting a post-pandemic recovery. At the same time, the number of active projects declined, suggesting increasing investment consolidation. Sectoral analysis shows that the energy sector remains dominant, followed by transport and information and communication technologies, while water supply and municipal solid waste sectors continue to demonstrate relatively lower investment performance. Regionally, East Asia and the Pacific lead global PPP investment activity, whereas other regions remain more dependent on external financial support.

Keywords: public-private partnership (PPP), infrastructure financing, private investment, development finance institutions (DFIs), export credit agencies, investment trends, risk sharing, emerging economies, sectoral analysis, regional disparities, infrastructure development, sustainable financing.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается трансформирующаяся роль государственно-частного партнёрства (ГЧП) в финансировании и реализации инфраструктурных проектов в различных регионах мира с особым акцентом на инвестиционные тенденции 2025 года. Исследуются динамика инвестиций в проекты ГЧП, их отраслевое распределение и региональные различия. Особое внимание уделяется восстановлению глобальных инвестиций в ГЧП после периода снижения, а также сохраняющейся концентрации капитала в ограниченном числе стран и отраслей. Отдельно анализируется роль международных финансовых институтов развития (DFIs) и экспортно-кредитных агентств в поддержке инфраструктурного финансирования в условиях повышенных рисков и ограниченного доступа к капиталу, особенно в странах, входящих в группу Международной ассоциации развития (IDA).

Результаты исследования показывают, что совокупный объём инвестиций в проекты ГЧП в 2025 году превысил 100 млрд долларов США, что свидетельствует о восстановлении инвестиционной активности после пандемии. Вместе с тем сокращение числа реализуемых проектов указывает на усиление концентрации инвестиций. Отраслевой анализ показывает, что лидирующие позиции по-прежнему занимает энергетический сектор, за которым следуют транспорт и информационно-коммуникационные технологии. В то же время сферы водоснабжения и обращения с твёрдыми коммунальными отходами продолжают демонстрировать относительно более низкие показатели инвестиционной активности. В региональном разрезе наибольший объём инвестиций в проекты ГЧП приходится на страны Восточной Азии и Тихоокеанского региона, тогда как другие регионы в большей степени зависят от внешней финансовой поддержки.

Ключевые слова: государственно-частное партнёрство (ГЧП), финансирование инфраструктуры, частные инвестиции, международные финансовые институты развития (DFIs), экспортно-кредитные агентства, инвестиционные тенденции, распределение рисков, развивающиеся экономики, отраслевой анализ, региональные различия, развитие инфраструктуры, устойчивое финансирование.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of increasing global uncertainty, geopolitical tensions, and the expansion of financial and economic restrictions, countries are increasingly encouraged to strengthen domestic economic integration, modernize infrastructure comprehensively, and improve the competitiveness of key economic sectors. According to the World Bank [1], investment mobilization for infrastructure projects in 2024 reached significant levels across major sectors: USD 67.9 billion was invested in 217 energy projects, USD 10.5 billion in the information and communication technology sector, and USD 20.6 billion in 38 transport projects. In addition, investments in the water supply sector amounted to USD 13 billion through the implementation of nine projects.

Against this background, expanding the financing of infrastructure projects through public-private partnerships (PPPs) in developing countries has become an important policy priority. PPP mechanisms play a significant role in ensuring sustainable economic growth by attracting private sector capital, accelerating economic modernization, strengthening integration into the international division of labor, supporting structural transformation, and creating new employment opportunities. Furthermore, PPP-based infrastructure development contributes to improving public service delivery, increasing investment efficiency, and reducing fiscal pressure on government budgets. Consequently, the effective mobilization of private investment through PPP frameworks is increasingly recognized as an important instrument for achieving long-term socio-economic development and strengthening national economic resilience in an uncertain global environment.

The improvement of financing mechanisms for public-private partnership (PPP) projects in Uzbekistan is a key priority for national economic development, investment attraction, and the implementation of large-scale infrastructure projects. A target has been set to attract USD 30 billion in PPP-related investments by 2030. Achieving this objective requires the development of a targeted portfolio of infrastructure projects in cooperation with international financial institutions, the formulation of appropriate financing conditions for investment projects, and the establishment of more effective forms of cooperation between the state and the private sector.

In this regard, particular attention is being paid to the formation of hybrid investment mechanisms aimed at mobilizing financial resources and supporting projects through innovative financing instruments. This includes the creation of a dedicated project support fund based on a hybrid model of investment mobilization, which represents an effective form of partnership between the government and small and medium-sized businesses. Such an approach increases the relevance of in-depth scientific research into the institutional, financial, and organizational aspects of PPP development, as well as the optimization of investment attraction mechanisms in the national economy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Within this research area, numerous domestic and international scholars have conducted extensive studies and presented both theoretical contributions and practical recommendations. In particular, according to economists Knüpfer and Werner, in the United States, public-private partnership (PPP) is defined as “a contractual arrangement between the public and private sectors that allows participation in public ownership and enables the performance of functions traditionally assigned to public authorities” [2].

Professor M. B. Gerrard, in his article “PPP, Finance and Development,” defines public-private partnerships as follows: “The combination of PPPs helps to improve the quality of public services or to manage public assets by mobilizing private capital and, in some cases, public capital as well” [3].

Another foreign economist, E. R. Yescombe, in his book *Public-Private Partnerships: Policy Principles and Finance*, describes PPPs as “long-term contractual relationships between public sector authorities and a private partner, or a consortium of private firms, for the development and utilization of infrastructure, in which the private partner is responsible for construction, management, service delivery, and financing” [4].

Professors U. Sharifkhujayev and D. Abdullaev, in their article “Public-Private Partnership and Its Structure,” conducted a comparative analysis of various definitions of PPPs and subsequently proposed their own authorial definition. According to them, “public-private partnership is a set of relations aimed at the efficient contractual involvement of the private sector in order to perform public-sector economic tasks more effectively, characterized by the allocation of costs, risks, mutual obligations, and powers between the two parties” [5].

Another domestic economist, DSc N. Shavkatov, who has conducted extensive research in this field, provides an authorial definition of PPP in his article “Public-Private Partnership Projects: Practice and Development Prospects.” Based on theoretical studies, he defines public-private partnership as “a form of strategic, institutional, economic, and financial cooperation between the public and private sectors aimed at implementing socially significant infrastructure projects and delivering public services.” He further notes that PPP represents partnership relations between two or more representatives of the public and private sectors in investment, infrastructure, and innovation projects, as well as in socio-economic, scientific, and other state-significant programs [6].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive and analytical research approach to examine global trends in public-private partnership (PPP) investments and infrastructure financing. The methodology is primarily based on the systematic analysis of secondary data obtained from international financial institutions, including reports and statistical databases of the World Bank and other development finance organizations.

The research applies comparative analysis to evaluate PPP investment dynamics across regions, countries, and sectors during the period 2021–2025. Quantitative indicators, including total investment volume, number of projects, and sectoral distribution, are analyzed to identify key trends, structural changes, and concentration patterns in global PPP activity. In addition, trend analysis is used to assess changes over time and determine post-pandemic recovery patterns in PPP investment flows.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the current context, the need to support large-scale reforms in Uzbekistan aimed at improving public welfare, enhancing living standards, and further developing cooperation between the public and private sectors is steadily increasing. As the experience of developing countries demonstrates, the practice of establishing public-private partnership (PPP) frameworks for infrastructure development and investment attraction has already proven its practical relevance. Increasing private sector participation in capital-intensive sectors of the economy remains one of the most important issues today.

The establishment of mutually beneficial cooperation between the public and private sectors can contribute to strengthening corporate social responsibility among economic actors. Such balanced cooperation is characterized by the fair distribution of risks, the assurance of profitability, and the protection of the rights and interests of both parties [7]. In general, corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the private sector is primarily reflected in the social protection of employees and their families, health and wellness programs, improvement of the working environment and surrounding areas, as well as the development and maintenance of social infrastructure facilities.

In this context, it should be emphasized that the development of science, innovation, and socially significant areas, including sports, is closely related to business social responsibility. From this perspective, greater attention should be paid to supporting the comprehensive development of the private sector in Uzbekistan. To achieve this, it is essential to create equal operating conditions for both public and private sector participants. As a result, the expansion of business activities can contribute to the formation of large-scale corporate structures within the national economy.

In our view, the following aspects related to the functioning and specific features of public-private partnership relations and corporate social responsibility are particularly relevant:

- The development of public-private partnership (PPP) relations contributes to the socio-economic development of the country by enabling the joint implementation of social and infrastructure projects through effective cooperation between the public and private sectors.
- Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is aimed at the voluntary implementation of specific social projects initiated by private sector entities. In this regard, the participation of corporate structures in such projects also serves as an instrument of social branding and public communication.
- Public-private partnership (PPP) relations and corporate social responsibility contribute to the expansion of investment relations. As a result, business entities gain opportunities to obtain both social and economic benefits, while certain public expenditures may be optimized.
- In Uzbekistan, public-private partnership (PPP) relations currently operate within a relatively limited scope. Given their significant social and economic importance, it is necessary to expand such partnerships across various sectors and industries. To increase the scale of corporate social responsibility in the private sector, it is advisable to ensure equal operating conditions for public and private sector participants, which in turn will support the sustainable development of private business.

The public-private partnership (PPP) mechanism is considered one of the alternative approaches to financing infrastructure development or modernization. As an alternative to traditional public procurement-based financing, PPPs can significantly accelerate infrastructure development processes. Although infrastructure projects are sometimes financed not from the state budget but by private partners through privately mobilized equity or debt capital via a PPP company, many projects still involve public sector financial support to attract and facilitate private sector participation. At the same time, many PPP arrangements may not affect public debt levels, provided that they meet specific criteria established by the national accounting standards of the respective country.

It is well known that the main internal sources of investment in an economy are, first of all, the state and private business entities operating within the country. Therefore, according to many economists, cooperation

between the public and private sectors in economic activity represents an institutional and organizational form of partnership aimed at attracting and implementing investments in socially and economically significant projects across a wide range of sectors. Since social challenges such as hunger, poverty, and social inequality cannot be resolved in the short term, the implementation of long-term investment and management strategies through public-private cooperation can contribute to the creation of high social value within the country [8].

Public-private partnership (PPP) is an institutional and organizational alliance between the state and private business aimed at implementing socially significant projects and programs across a wide range of sectors, from scientific research to service delivery. The efficiency achieved in the implementation of PPP-based projects can be classified into three main types:

Economic efficiency generally refers to the profit generated by the private sector. In partnership relations, the additional value created through private sector participation can be reflected precisely in economic efficiency.

Political efficiency refers to the achievement of the state's domestic and foreign policy objectives as a result of public-private partnership (PPP) arrangements.

Social efficiency refers to the improvement of public welfare, access to quality services, and the development of social infrastructure through the joint participation of the public and private sectors.

The experience of developed countries shows that public-private partnership (PPP) relations play a significant role in promoting economic development, ensuring the effective implementation of large-scale infrastructure projects, and improving social infrastructure within the country. In this regard, studying the experience of developing countries and adapting their practical approaches to national conditions is considered an important task.

In 2025, global public-private partnership (PPP) investments recovered after several years of decline, while continuing to demonstrate significant regional disparities. In regions characterized by high geopolitical, macroeconomic, and regulatory uncertainty, such as the Middle East and North Africa, Europe and Central Asia, and South Asia, PPP activity was primarily supported by the involvement of development finance institutions and export credit agencies.

Although the overall volume of public-private partnership (PPP) activity in the Middle East and North Africa region declined, nearly all projects in the region — 7 out of 8 — were supported by development finance institutions and export credit agencies. This once again confirms their important role in mobilizing private capital by reducing risks in complex investment environments (Table 1).

Table 1
Information on Financing Infrastructure Projects Based on Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) in Regions

Regions	PPP investment volume in 2025 (in USD)	PPP investment volume in 2023 (in USD)	PPP investment volume (2021–2025)	Financing Infrastructure Projects under Public-Private Partnership (PPP) in 2025	Infrastructure Project Financing under Public-Private Partnership (PPP), 2021–2025
East Asia and Pacific Region	57.0	51.4	36.0	10%	9%
Europe and Central Asia Region	7.7	4.1	5.6	82%	40%
Latin America and the Caribbean Region	21.9	16.1	22.3	18%	24%
Middle East and North Africa Region	0.5	2.9	2.6	88%	59%
South Asia Region	5.7	9.3	11.8	39%	34%
Sub-Saharan Africa Region	7.9	3.4	5.4	64%	67%
TOTAL:	100.7	87.2	83.7	34%	28%

Compiled by the author based on data from the World Bank Annual Report.

In contrast, despite the overall recovery observed in low- and middle-income countries in 2025, public-private partnership (PPP) investments in International Development Association (IDA) countries declined to USD 3.0 billion across 33 projects. This represents a 38 percent decrease in PPP investments in 2025 and a 57 percent decline compared with the five-year average.

It is noteworthy that 88 percent of projects in International Development Association (IDA) countries relied on support from development finance institutions and export credit agencies. This once again confirms their important role in maintaining investment flows in infrastructure financing under conditions of limited private capital.

In 2025, private sector participation in infrastructure through public-private partnerships (PPPs) reached USD 100.7 billion. This represents a 16 percent increase compared with USD 87.1 billion in the previous year and is 20 percent higher than the five-year average of USD 83.7 billion. At the same time, this was the first time since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic that PPP investments exceeded the USD 100 billion threshold.

Despite the increase in investment volume, the number of projects slightly declined, decreasing from 324 in 2024 to 315 in 2025 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Investments and Projects¹

In 2025, private infrastructure investment commitments increased across several sectors compared to the previous year. The energy sector remained the leading area, accounting for USD 67.9 billion across 217 projects. The information and communication technology (ICT) sector reached a record level of USD 10.5 billion; however, these funds were distributed across fewer projects compared to 2024 (Table 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of Private Infrastructure Investment Commitments by Sector (2024–2025)

Sectors and Industries	PPP 2025 (USD billion)	Number of projects in 2025	PPP 2024 (USD billion)	Number of projects in 2024
Energy	67.9	217	63.7	189
Transport	20.6	38	13.7	46
AKT	10.5	32	7.8	59
Water Supply	1.3	19	1.8	19
Soled Waste	0.3	9	0.1	11

Compiled by the author based on official data from the World Bank.

¹ Compiled by the author based on data from the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the World Bank.

The transport sector recorded growth, reaching USD 20.6 billion across 38 projects; however, it still remained below its historical peak levels. The municipal solid waste sector recovered to USD 326 million across nine projects, although it continued to remain below previous high levels. In contrast, the water sector declined to USD 1.3 billion, continuing its gradual downward trend.

In 2025, the number of countries with PPP investment commitments decreased from 68 in 2024 to 58. This indicates a higher concentration of investments in a smaller number of countries. The trend is partly explained by a significant increase in investment activity in the East Asia and Pacific region. In particular, China, Malaysia, and the Philippines accounted for 53 percent of total PPP commitments, representing the largest share.

At the same time, two countries — Equatorial Guinea and Guyana — recorded PPP transactions for the first time in more than a decade. In both cases, these agreements were associated with port infrastructure modernization projects.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted analysis demonstrates that public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms remain a crucial instrument for financing and implementing infrastructure development projects in both developed and developing economies. Despite fluctuations in global investment trends, PPP investments in 2025 showed a clear recovery after several years of decline, exceeding the USD 100 billion threshold for the first time since the COVID-19 pandemic. However, this recovery is characterized by an uneven distribution of investments across regions, countries, and sectors.

The findings highlight significant regional disparities. East Asia and the Pacific region dominate global PPP activity, while regions such as the Middle East and North Africa, Europe and Central Asia, and South Asia continue to rely heavily on development finance institutions (DFIs) and export credit agencies to mitigate investment risks and mobilize private capital. This underscores the continued importance of international financial institutions in supporting infrastructure development in high-risk environments, particularly in International Development Association (IDA) countries, where investment volumes have declined despite reliance on external financial support.

Sectoral analysis reveals that the energy sector remains the leading area in terms of PPP investment commitments, followed by transport and information and communication technologies (ICT). Meanwhile, the water supply and municipal solid waste sectors demonstrate weaker and more volatile investment performance. At the same time, the reduction in the number of participating countries, combined with higher investment concentration in a limited group of economies, indicates a growing polarization of global PPP activity.

Overall, the study confirms that PPPs are increasingly becoming a strategic tool for mobilizing private capital, improving infrastructure efficiency, and reducing fiscal pressure on governments. Nevertheless, several persistent challenges remain, including regional inequality in investment distribution, sectoral imbalances, and dependence on external financial institutions in developing economies. Therefore, strengthening institutional frameworks, improving risk-sharing mechanisms, and expanding equal investment conditions between the public and private sectors are essential for ensuring the sustainable development of PPP-driven infrastructure financing at the global level.

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Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Hasan Maqsudov

2026. № 6

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